

Effect of Intracanal Medicaments (Triple Antibiotic Paste, Modified Triple Antibiotic Paste, & Odontopaste) On Microhardness of Root Dentin: An In Vitro Study

Deepshikha Mishra¹
Malwika Sisodiya²
V.K. Shetty³
Debangna Bhushan Sarma⁴
Gargee Roy Choudhury⁵

PG Student¹
Department of Conservative Dentistry
& Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry &
Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

Professor²
Department of Conservative Dentistry
& Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry &
Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

Professor & Head³
Department of Conservative Dentistry
& Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry &
Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

PG Student⁴
Department of Conservative Dentistry
& Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry &
Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

PG Student⁵
Department of Conservative Dentistry
& Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry &
Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

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Abstract

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate and compare the impact of three intracanal medicaments triple antibiotic paste (TAP), modified triple antibiotic paste (MTAP), and odontopaste on the microhardness of root dentin.

Materials and Methods: A total of 76 extracted mandibular bicuspid with a single root and single canal were prepared using ProTaper Next rotary files. The samples were divided into four groups: three experimental groups (n = 19 each) and one untreated control group (n = 19). The experimental groups received TAP, MTAP, and odontopaste within the root canals. After 21 days, the medicaments were removed using an Endo Activator. The mean Knoop hardness values were then measured and compared with those of the control group. Statistical analysis was performed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, one-way ANOVA, and Student's t-test.

Results: All experimental groups, except the odontopaste group, showed a significant reduction (p < 0.05) in root dentin microhardness compared to the control group. The odontopaste group demonstrated the least reduction, which was not statistically significant (p > 0.05).

Conclusion: Odontopaste appears to be more favorable as it has minimal impact on the microhardness of root dentin when compared to TAP and MTAP.

Clinical Significance: Successful endodontic treatment depends on effective elimination of bacterial infection from the root canal while preserving the structural integrity of dentin. Odontopaste shows potential in achieving both objectives; however, further in vivo studies are necessary to validate these findings.

Keywords: Odontopaste, Triple Antibiotic Paste, Modified triple antibiotic paste, Microhardness, Root dentin.

Introduction

Root canal infections involve a complex mix of aerobic and anaerobic microorganisms, making their complete elimination challenging. Due to the intricate anatomy of the root canal system, mechanical cleaning and shaping alone cannot fully disinfect the canal. Therefore, intracanal medicaments are essential to further reduce microbial load as part of an effective endodontic protocol, alongside biomechanical preparation and irrigation^{1,2}.

Intracanal medicaments are particularly important in persistent infections, where anatomical variations such as fins and accessory canals protect bacteria from conventional cleaning methods. Since a single antibiotic is often insufficient, Triple Antibiotic Paste (TAP) is commonly used for its broad spectrum antimicrobial action and ability to promote tissue healing and regeneration^{3,4,5}.

However, prolonged use of TAP can weaken dentin by reducing its microhardness, potentially increasing fracture risk. To address issues like discoloration and structural dama-

ge, Modified Triple Antibiotic Paste (MTAP), which replaces minocycline with clindamycin, has been developed and used successfully in regenerative procedures⁶.

Odontopaste is another intracanal medicament that contains clindamycin, triamcinolone, and calcium hydroxide. It helps reduce inflammation, relieve pain, and control bacterial growth without causing tooth discoloration. Importantly, it has minimal impact on dentin's mechanical properties, including microhardness⁷.

Although higher concentrations of antibiotic pastes are effective, they may be harmful to stem cells. Hence, lower concentrations are now recommended to balance antimicrobial efficacy and biocompatibility^{8,9}.

Despite these advancements, intracanal medicaments can still negatively affect dentin

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properties, including reduced microhardness and fracture resistance over time¹⁰. Therefore, selecting an ideal medicament that effectively eliminates bacteria while preserving dentin integrity remains crucial. This study aims to compare the effects of TAP, MTAP, and Odontopaste on root dentin microhardness.

Material and Methods

The study was conducted in the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics at Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre, Gwalior. A total of 76 freshly extracted single rooted, single canal teeth were collected, excluding teeth with caries, fractures, curved, calcified, or obliterated canals. Samples were stored in an incubator and divided into four groups (n=19 each): Triple Antibiotic Paste (TAP), Modified TAP (MTAP), Odontopaste, and a control group without medicament.

Teeth were disinfected with 2% chlorhexidine, decoronated at the cemento-enamel junction, and instrumented using ProTaper Next rotary files up to size F4. Root canals were irrigated with 1% sodium hypochlorite and 17% EDTA. TAP (ciprofloxacin, metronidazole, minocycline in 1:1:1 ratio), MTAP (metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, clindamycin), and Odontopaste (clindamycin with triamcinolone) were placed in respective groups for 14 days using a lentulospiral, while the control group received no medicament. Samples were sealed and incubated at 37°C.

Figure 1. (a) Decoronation at the cemento-enamel junction using a diamond disc of 16 mm. (b) the roots measured at the length of junction using a ruler.

After 14 days, medicaments were removed using an Endo Activator and NaOCl, followed by distilled water irrigation. Roots were sectioned into 2-mm slices and mounted in resin. Dentine microhardness was evaluated using a Knoop indenter, with three measurements taken per sample and averaged.

Figure 2 (a) Microhardness testing of dentin samples. (b) Microscopic view of indentations and measurement of Knoop Hardness Number

All procedures were performed by a single investigator, while microhardness testing was conducted by a blinded examiner. Data were analyzed using SPSS v26.0. Results were expressed as mean ± SD, normality was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, and comparisons were made using one way ANOVA and Student's t-test, with significance set at p < 0.05.

Results

Microhardness was assessed using a Knoop microhardness tester, and the mean Knoop Hardness Number (KHN) was calculated for each specimen. Table 1 shows the results of the Kolmogorov Smirnov test used to assess the normality of distribution of microhardness values in all four groups. The test revealed that Group 1 (p = 0.200), Group 2 (p = 0.200), Group 3 (p = 0.200), and Group 4 (p = 0.200) had p-values greater than 0.05. Since all groups demonstrated non-significant p-values, the data were considered normally distributed. Therefore, parametric tests were applied for further statistical analysis.

Table 1: Normality test

Group	Statistic	Degree of Freedom	P value
Group 1	.088	19	.200 ^a
Group 2	.105	19	.200 ^a
Group 3	.128	19	.200 ^a
Group 4	.142	19	.200 ^a

Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, ^anon-significant

Table 2, Graph 1 presents the comparison of mean microhardness values among the four groups using One-way ANOVA. The mean microhardness in Group 1 (TAP) was 50.74 ± 1.93, in Group 2 (MTAP) was 59.83 ± 2.15, in Group 3 (Odontopaste) was 69.83 ± 2.17, and in Group 4 (Control) was 82.63 ± 2.65. The ANOVA test showed a highly statistically significant difference among the groups (F = 707.99, p = 0.001). This indicates that the type of intracanal medicament had a significant effect on the microhardness of radicular dentin after 14 days.

Table 2: Comparison of microhardness of root dentin between groups

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F value	P value
Group 1	19	50.74	1.93	707.99	0.001*
Group 2	19	59.83	2.15		
Group 3	19	69.83	2.17		
Group 4	19	82.63	2.65		

One way ANOVA, *Significant

Graph 1: Comparison of microhardness of root dentin between groups

Discussion

Due to the complex root canal anatomy, biomechanical preparation alone cannot completely eliminate microorganisms. Residual bacteria can repopulate within 2–4 days, with Enterococcus faecalis being particularly resistant and commonly linked to persistent periapical lesions. Hence, intracanal medicaments are recommended, typically used for 1–4 weeks for disinfection and

up to 11 weeks in regenerative procedures^{13,14}.

An ideal intracanal medicament should be non-irritating, prevent tooth discoloration, exhibit strong antimicrobial properties with good biocompatibility, and support long-term peri radicular tissue healing. However, prolonged use may reduce radicular dentin microhardness, as reported by Prather et al., likely due to disruption of the bond between hydroxyapatite and collagen, weakening dentin structure¹⁵.

This study aims to compare the effects of Triple Antibiotic Paste, Modified Triple Antibiotic Paste, and Odontopaste on dentin microhardness. Using single rooted mandibular premolars with relatively uniform canal anatomy allows standardized instrumentation and minimizes variability from complex root structures. Single rooted mandibular premolars were selected due to their uniform anatomy, ease of sectioning, and consistent dentin thickness, allowing reliable microhardness assessment^{23,25}.

Chlorhexidine (2%) was used for storage due to its broad antimicrobial activity against organisms like *E. faecalis* and *A. israelii*. Decoronation standardized samples by removing the crown, improving access, instrumentation, and reproducibility.

ProTaper Next rotary files were used as they provide flexibility without affecting fracture resistance. Sodium hypochlorite (1%) was chosen for irrigation due to lower cytotoxicity, while 17% EDTA was used to effectively remove the smear layer²².

Irrigants such as NaOCl and chlorhexidine can reduce dentin microhardness. Temporary sealing with Cavit simulated clinical conditions and prevented excessive chemical exposure.

Triple Antibiotic Paste (TAP) shows strong antimicrobial effects but significantly reduces dentin microhardness due to demineralization, mainly from minocycline. Modified TAP (MTAP) reduces discoloration but still lowers microhardness due to its acidic nature. Odontopaste, containing clindamycin and triamcinolone, offers effective antimicrobial action with comparatively less impact on dentin structure^{17,19}.

Removal of medicaments is essential before obturation, though complete removal is difficult; sonic systems like the Endo Activator are more effective. Microhardness testing using Knoop/Vickers methods is simple and reliable, typically performed after 14 days of medicament application^{6,8}.

There are certain limitations associated with this study. First, it was conducted as an in-vitro experiment using extracted teeth; therefore, the results may differ from clinical conditions where teeth interact with the oral environment. Additionally, vital teeth may respond differently due to physiological functions that cannot be fully replicated in laboratory conditions. Second, the results might vary depending on whether the medicament was placed up to the root apex, as the penetration depth of each medicament was not evaluated in this study.

Conclusion

Within the limitations of this in vitro study, it can be concluded that the successful use of intracanal medicament primarily depends on eliminating most microorganisms from the root canal while causing little to no alteration in the microhardness of the root dentin. A key step in decreasing microbial load before obturation is the application of an appropriate intracanal medicament. Numerous medicaments have been evaluated for this purpose. In the present study, odontopaste has demonstrated encouraging antimicrobial effectiveness with minimal impact on the microhardness of root dentin as compared to Triple antibiotic paste (TAP), Modified Triple Antibiotic Paste (MTAP).

References

1. Parashar V, Khan SA, Singh P, Sharma S, Kumar A, Kumar A. Effect of Intracanal Medicaments (Modified Triple Antibiotic Paste, Calcium Hydroxide, and Aloe Vera) on Microhardness of Root Dentine: An In Vitro Study. *J Contemp Dent Pract.* 2020 Jun 1;21(6): 632-635. PMID: 33025931.
2. Malu K, Khubchandani M (September 15, 2022) Triple Antibiotic Paste: A Suitable Medicament for Intracanal Disinfection. *Cureus* 14(9): e29186. DOI 10.7759/cureus.29186.
3. Prather BT, Ehrlich Y, Spolnik K, et al. Effects of two combinations of triple antibiotic paste used in endodontic regeneration on root microhardness and chemical structure of radicular dentine. *J Oral Sci* 2014; 56 (4): 245–251.
4. Salama, A Salama and Aya a Salama. "Root Canal Medicaments - Literature Review". *Acta Scientific Medical Sciences* 4.3 (2020): 102-106.
5. Cochrane, S, and Burrow, MF, et al. "Effect on the mechanical properties of human and bovine dentine of intracanal medicaments and irrigants". *Australian Dental Journal*, vol.64, no.1, 2019, pp. 35-42.
6. Chuenarrom C, Benjakul P, Daosodsai P. Effect of indentation load and time on Knoop and Vickers microhardness tests for enamel and dentin. *Mat Res [Internet]*. 2009;12 (4): 473–6.
7. Kumar S, Desai K, Palekar A, Biradar B, Chatterjee A, Kumari K. Comparison of the Efficacy of Canal Brush, Endo Activator, and Passive Ultrasonic Irrigation on the Removal of Triple Antibiotic Paste from Root Canal Walls: An In Vitro Study. *J Int Soc Prev Community Dent.* 2020 Aug 6;10(4): 424-430.
8. Voort GFV and Lucas GM. Micro indentation Hardness Testing. *Advanced Materials & Processes.* 1998; 154(5):21-25.
9. Nogueira APA, Grazziotin-Soares R, Leal AMM, Freitas Júnior SAG, Gonçalves BLL, Bauer J, Ferreira MC, Carvalho CN. Root Canal Dentin Microhardness after Contact with Antibiotic Medications: An In Vitro Study. *Dent J (Basel).* 2024 Jun 29;12 (7): 201. Doi: 10.3390/dj12070201. PMID: 39056988; PMCID: PMC11276266.
10. Daneswari M, Reddy NV, Chris AP, Reddy NV, Kondamadugu S, Niharika P. a Comparative Evaluation of Microhardness and Chemical Structure of Radicular Dentin with Two Combinations of TAP and MTAP: An In Vitro Study. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent* 2022; 15 (S2): S151-S157.
11. Eldeniz AU, Erdemir A, Belli S. Effect of EDTA and citric acid solutions on the microhardness and the roughness of human root canal dentin. *J Endod.* 2005 Feb;31(2):107-10. Doi: 10.1097/01.don.0000136212.53475.ad. PMID: 15671820.
12. Oliveira LD, Carvalho CA, Nunes W, Valera MC, Camargo CH, Jorge AO. Effects of chlorhexidine and sodium hypochlorite on the microhardness of root canal dentin. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod.* 2007 Oct;104(4): e125-8. Doi: 10.1016/j.tripleo.2007.04.019. Epub 2007 Jul 26. PMID: 17656125.
13. Bolla, N., Kavuri, S.R., Tanniru, H.I., Vemuri, S. and Shenoy, A. (2012) Comparative Evaluation of Antimicrobial Efficacy of Odontopaste, Chlorhexidine and Propolis as Root Canal Medicaments against *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Candida albicans*. *Journal of International Dental and Medical Research*, 5, 14-25.
14. Eftekhari B, Moghimipour E, Pourakbar Jahandideh P, Jalali S, Mahmoudian M. Analgesic effect of odontopaste and a compound intracanal medicament between root canal therapy

- appointments. *Jundishapur J Nat Pharm Prod.* 2013 Nov; 8 (4):169-74. Doi: 10.17795/jjnpp-12473. Epub 2013 Nov 1. PMID: 24624209; PMCID: PMC3941894.
15. Prabhakar A, Taur S, Hadakar S, Sugandhan S. Comparison of Antibacterial Efficacy of Calcium Hydroxide Paste, 2% Chlorhexidine Gel and Turmeric Extract as an Intracanal Medicament and their Effect on Microhardness of Root Dentin: An in vitro Study. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent.* 2013 Sep; 6 (3):171-7. Doi: 10.5005/jp-journals-10005-1213. Epub 2013 Oct 14. PMID: 25206217; PMCID: PMC4086604.
 16. Bhandari S, T S A, Patil CR. An in Vitro Evaluation of Antimicrobial Efficacy of 2% Chlorhexidine Gel, Propolis and Calcium Hydroxide Against *Enterococcus faecalis* in Human Root Dentin. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2014 Nov; 8 (11): ZC60-3. Doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2014/10359.5144. Epub 2014 Nov 20. PMID: 25584319; PMCID: PMC4290330.
 17. Yassen GH, Eckert GJ, Platt JA. Effect of intracanal medicaments used in endodontic regeneration procedures on microhardness and chemical structure of dentin. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2015 May; 40(2):104-12. Doi: 10.5395/rde.2015.40.2.104. Epub 2014 Dec 24. PMID: 25984471; PMCID: PMC4432252.
 18. Yaduka Pallavi & Sharma Subash. (2021). Novel intracanal medicaments and it's future scope.
 19. Chen BK, George R, Walsh LJ. Discoloration of roots caused by residual endodontic intracanal medicaments. *Scientific World Journal.* 2014 Feb 9; 2014:404676. Doi: 10.1155/2014/404676. PMID: 24688386; PMCID: PMC3934450.
 20. Aslantas EE, Buzoglu HD, Altundasar E, Serper A. Effect of EDTA, sodium hypochlorite, and chlorhexidine gluconate with or without surface modifiers on dentin microhardness. *J Endod.* 2014 Jun; 40 (6): 876-9. Doi: 10.1016/j.joen.2013.10.041. Epub 2014 Apr 13. PMID: 24862721.
 21. Akman M, Akbulut MB, Edinberg HA, Belli S. Comparison of different irrigation activation regimens and conventional irrigation techniques for the removal of modified triple antibiotic paste from root canals. *J Endod.* 2015 May; 41 (5): 720-4. Doi: 10.1016/j.joen.2015.01.001. Epub 2015 Mar 5. PMID: 25747378.
 22. Brito, Patricia & Lima, Patricia & Silva, Emmanuel & Fidel, Sandra & Fidel, Rivail & Sassone, Luciana. (2016). Effectiveness of ProTaper Next, ProTaper Universal and WaveOne systems in reducing intracanal bacterial load. *Endodontic practice.* 10. 167-173.
 23. Saha SG, Sharma V, Bharadwaj A, Shrivastava P, Saha MK, Dubey S, Kala S, Gupta S. Effectiveness of Various Endodontic Irrigants on the Micro-Hardness of the Root Canal Dentin: An in vitro Study. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2017 Apr; 11(4): ZC01-ZC04. Doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2017/24018.9472. Epub 2017 Apr 1. PMID: 28571249; PMCID: PMC5449895.
 24. Zargar N, Rayat Hosein Abadi M, Sabeti M, Yadegari Z, Akbarzadeh Baghban A, Dianat O. Antimicrobial efficacy of clindamycin and triple antibiotic paste as root canal medicaments on tubular infection: An in vitro study. *Aust Endod J.* 2019 Apr; 45 (1): 86-91. Doi: 10.1111/aej.12288. Epub 2018 Aug 16. PMID: 30113736.
 25. Unnikrishnan M, Mathai V, Sadasiva K, Santakumari RSM, Girish S, Shailajakumari AK. The Evaluation of Dentin Microhardness After Use of 17% EDTA, 17% EGTA, 10% Citric Acid, MTAD Used as Chelating Agents Combined With 2.5% Sodium Hypochlorite After Rotary Instrumentation: An In Vitro SEM Study. *J Pharm Bio Allied Sci.* 2019 May; 11(Suppl 2): S156 S163. Doi: 10.4103/JPBS.JPBS_282_18. PMID: 31198329; PMCID: PMC6555366.